

Learning Design Based on Systemic Functional Linguistics and Student Learning Style

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Abstract

This study is based on a qualitative approach. The method used is a literature review and survey. A literature review was conducted to determine the features of e-learning, the right approach, and the characteristics of teaching Indonesian for foreign speakers (BIPA) according to the learning styles of BIPA students. The survey was conducted to determine the learning styles of BIPA students. Respondents in this study were 25 BIPA students. The survey was conducted from July 28 to August 6, 2021. The results showed that the most dominant learning style is tactile/kinesthetic learning style 4.4, followed by Visual/nonverbal learning style (4.3), Audio/verbal learning style (4.14), and the smallest is Visual/verbal learning style. (4).

1. Introduction

Technology has an extensive influence on human life, including in education. Indonesian language learning for foreign speakers is also greatly affected by technological developments. Technology is an inseparable part of learning Indonesian for foreign speakers (BIPA). Technology not only supports education but even becomes a substitute for face-to-face meetings.

Teaching languages and researching Indonesian for foreign speakers have been done quite a lot. However, the development of teaching materials and research carried out so far is in the context of learning Indonesian in the classroom face to face. Research on learning Indonesian for foreign speakers conducted online has not been widely carried out, even though technology in learning has been widely carried out and provides great potential for optimizing the quality of language learning.

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The use of technology in learning, especially language learning, is not new. Technology has been used in language learning since the 1990s, and since then, the use of the internet in learning has increased (Alizadeh, 2012; Escobar Fandiño et al., 2019).

Technology provides many advantages that can help improve learning, including language learning. In this article, technology in learning is limited to e-learning, especially in learning Indonesian for foreign speakers. The advantages of technology, especially e-learning, include many aspects such as more interactive learning (Dharmawati, 2017; Mutambik, 2018), more motivation to learn (Escobar Fandiño et al., 2019; Harandi, 2015; Mohammadi et al., 2011), can reduce the gap in access to information (Acharya & Lee, 2018). Technology reduces costs, increasing the availability of training, integrating content that makes learning more exciting and effective, providing learners who are tailored to their needs and access to learning that is flexible in terms of time and place (Aydin & Tasci, 2005; Hasyim & Haling, 2017; Jan et al., 2012; Mutambik, 2018), improve the quality of language learning (Coopasami et al., 2017; Escobar Fandiño et al., 2019).

E-learning can be utilized in various ways, involving asynchronous, synchronous, and blended learning (Horton, 2012; Vai & Sosulski, 2015). E-learning activities can also take standalone courses, learning games and simulations, mobile learning, social learning, and virtual classroom courses (Horton, 2012). The design and types of e-learning activities are primarily determined by the objectives to be achieved, the available resources, and the needs and characteristics of course participants.

The advantages of technology are not without problems. The advantages possessed by technology do not automatically make learning with technology successful. The use of technology in education also has several challenges, such as having to design learning well (Gagné et al., 2005; Horton & Horton, 2003; Vai & Sosulski, 2015), the high initial cost of developing e-learning (Sampson et al., 2018), requires mastery of technology (Aydin & Tasci, 2005; Escobar Fandiño et al., 2019; Vai & Sosulski, 2015), and time management problems (Vai & Sosulski, 2015).

In addition to considering the advantages of technology and anticipating problems in its application, the critical things that must be prepared carefully in designing online learning are analysis of needs, learning styles, costs, time, and value-add of e-learning (Fee, 2009). In language teaching, linguistic approaches and teaching methods are also essential to consider when designing learning designs.

In this article, the linguistic approach used in designing learning is the systemic functional linguistic (SFL) approach. The SFL approach gave birth to a learning approach called a text-based approach or a genre-based approach (GBA) (Emilia, 2016). From the SFL perspective, language teaching focuses on meaning, not just a set of rules, and is suitable for adult and child learners (Byrnes, 2009; Chaisiri, 2010). Text-based learning is very commonly applied, especially in learning English. Research shows that applying a text-based approach has a very positive influence on learning. The positive impact of the SFL approach on learning can be described as follows: helping to design the curriculum (Beverley Derewianka & Jones, 2010a; Francis John Troyan et al., 2021), assisting the professional development of teachers (Beverley Derewianka & Jones, 2010a), creating contextual learning (Francis J. Troyan et al., 2019), creating equality in education (Francis John Troyan et al., 2021), improve writing skills (Albino, 2017; Chaisiri, 2010; Emilia & Hamied, 2015; Pujiyanto et al., 2014; Syarifah & Gunawan, 2016; Thongchalerms & Jarunthawatchai, 2020), enhance understanding of the structure and meaning of the text (Albino, 2017; Nagao, 2018; Pujiyanto et al., 2014), create more effective learning (Ali et al., 2017; Kalali & Pishkar, 2015), and improve students' communicative skills in both oral and written communication (Francis J. Troyan et al., 2019). Although proven effective in language learning, text-based or systemic linguistic-based approaches have not been widely applied in learning Indonesian for foreign speakers. Because of these advantages, Learning Indonesian for foreign speakers based on SFL is essential to develop.

If language learning is to be conducted online, the characteristics of online learning must also be considered. Online learning has different characteristics from face-to-face learning. Applying the SFL approach in online learning requires adequate study and preparation. Before applying the SFL approach in BIPA learning, the things that must be considered are student learning styles, learning activities to be carried out, and appropriate technology to carry out teaching. This study aims to explore the design of Indonesian language learning for foreign speakers online, applying a systemic functional linguistic approach by considering students' learning styles.

2. Previous Studies

Several studies have been conducted on BIPA learning and developing BIPA teaching materials. There are 12 (two) studies on BIPA learning and the development of BIPA teaching materials that the author found. All research aims to develop BIPA teaching materials and face-to-face learning contexts (Adnyani et al., 2014; Arumdyahsari et al., 2016; Fariqoh, 2016; Gatot, 2014; Kusmiatun, Suyitno, Hs, et al., 2017; Kusmiatun, Suyitno, Hs., et al., 2017; Prasetyo, 2015; Ramadhani et al., 2016; Saddhono et al., 2019; Siroj, 2015; Suyitno et al., 2019). No research aims to develop learning tools, and no research that develops teaching materials to apply online learning. Learning Indonesian for foreign speakers online has different characteristics from face-to-face learning. Therefore, adequate studies are needed to carry out online BIPA learning.

Many studies examine the application of SFL in learning. Based on seventeen (17) studies, it is known that the application of SFL approach in learning has various positive impacts, among others, it can improve writing skills (Chaisiri, 2010b; Emilia & Hamied, 2015; Pujianto et al., 2014; Rohayani et al., 2015; S Thongchalerm & Jarunthawatchai, 2020) make learning more effective (Ali et al., 2017; Allen, 2007; Horton, 2012), 3) improving understanding of text structure and meaning (Nagao, 2018; Pujianto et al., 2014), helped design the curriculum (Nagao, 2018; Pujianto et al., 2014), increase positive attitudes in learning (Chaisiri, 2010b), increase literacy (Ertmer & Newby, 2013), 7) increase academic success (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014), develop teacher professionalism (Beverley Derewianka & Jones, 2010a), 9) create equality in the classroom (Francis John Troyan et al., 2021), and help develop material (Beverley Derewianka & Jones, 2010b). However, the various advantages of the SFL approach are the results of research in English language learning. Research in the context of Indonesian learning for non-native speakers has not yet been found. Therefore, research on applying the SFL approach in BIPA learning is very interesting and important.

Research on e-learning and its application in learning has also been carried out. Based on these studies, it can be seen that the application of e-learning in education has many positive effects. However, it cannot be separated from the various challenges that need to be mentioned above. The advantages gained by implementing e-learning include flexible learning both in terms of time and place (Aydin & Tasci, 2005; Rohayani et al., 2015), expanding access, enabling the integration of several types of content, providing materials as needed (Jan et al., 2012), increase learning success (Escobar Fandiño et al., 2019) and can adapt to learning styles (Fee, 2009; Jan et al., 2012). However, the application of e-learning in learning also presents several challenges, such as limited infrastructure (Aydin and Tasci, 2005; Kihzoza et al., 2016), high initial costs (Sampson et al., 2018), skills in using technology and learning management systems. (LMS), difficulties in designing effective online learning, difficulties in time management (Vai and Sosulski, 2015), unpreparedness to change (Kihzoza et al., 2016), and need more motivation to participate in online learning (Hasyim and Haling, 2017; Elaish et al., 2019).

The various advantages provided by the application of online learning are proof that online learning needs to be applied in BIPA learning. A good assessment and preparation can overcome the challenges of preparing and implementing online.

3. Theoretical Framework

Second language learning

Views on second language learning vary widely. These views can be grouped into behaviourism, cognitivism, and constructivism. (Allen, 2007), structural, communicative, and functional (Ertmer & Newby, 2013), early approaches (such as contrastive analysis, error analysis, and interlanguage), universal grammar, and functional approaches (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014). In addition, the second language learning approach can also be classified into behaviourism approach, cognitivism approach, humanism approach, and constructivism approach (Acharya & Lee, 2018; Aydin & Tasci, 2005; Harandi, 2015; Jan et al., 2012; Mohammadi et al., 2011), as well as groups with traditional grammar, functional systemic grammar, and functional- notional (Beverley Derewianka & Jones, 2010a).

The learning approach can be classified into behaviourism, cognitivism, and constructivism. Each learning approach has characteristics that make it suitable for specific learning purposes. Behaviourism: knowing content (knowing WHAT), effective cognitivism for problem-solving (knowing HOW), and constructivism is suitable for problems that are not so obvious that they are solved through reflection and action (Allen, 2007; Ertmer & Newby, 2013).

Systemic Functional Linguistics and Language Teaching

Systemic functional linguistics is a perspective and analysis of language that assumes that language is a system and functional. The word systemic contains the word system, which refers to the system of choice. The system is a paradigmatic pattern of language that contains several alternatives that can be chosen in the use of language. Meanwhile, functional implies that language is in the context of use, and language forms carry out certain functions (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014; Wiratno, 2018).

In the view of systemic functional linguistics, the language being used is text. Text is a meaningful language and is used in context. Text is always produced in a specific context. Context changes will cause text changes (Jones & Lock, 2011). Texts can be in the form of written or spoken language use. Because texts are so tied to their context, language teaching should also pay attention to context. Language teaching must also provide an understanding of the language context and language use. Understanding the context will help language learners understand the language used correctly and produce language appropriately.

In the systemic functional linguistic approach, language use's context can be divided into situational and cultural contexts (Halliday and Matthiessen, 2014). The context of the situation that significantly affects the use of language consists of three aspects: field, mode, and tenor (Eggins, 2004; Emilia, 2016; Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014; Thompson, 2014). In learning, the Systemic functional linguistic approach has several characteristics: staged, goal-oriented, and social (J. R. Martin, 2009). More specifically, the characteristics of learning by applying the LSF approach have the characteristics of explicit learning, linking spoken and written texts with the social and cultural context of their use, designing learning activities that focus on skill development, and guiding students to develop communicative language skills through full text (Agustien, 2020).

The use of the SFL approach in learning is related to and in line with several other language learning approaches, including the communicative approach (Emilia, 2016; Wiratno, 2018), the contextual approach, and the grammar of translation (Emilia, 2016). The stages of learning with a text-based approach have several variations of the model. These varied models share the same principles that emphasize the importance of building knowledge about the topic, providing a model as a reference, cooperation, especially when learning new texts, and the importance of the individual

instruction stage (Emilia, 2016). The learning steps generally consist of building knowledge of the field, modelling, joint construction, and independent construction (Agustien, 2020; Chaisiri, 2010; Emilia, 2016; Lo & Jeong, 2018; J. R. Martin, 2009).

E-learning

E-learning is delivered through a computer with a CD-ROM, internet, or intranet with several characteristics (Clark & Mayer, 2008). First, having teaching materials and activities relevant to the learning objectives. Second, use learning methods, examples, and exercises to help to learn. Third, using media such as words, pictures, and others to convey the material being taught. Fourth, learning can be carried out synchronously or asynchronously. Fifth, forming new knowledge or skills related to individual learning objectives or building group performance. E-learning is a system. An e-learning system contains three information system components: people, technologies, and services (Aparicio et al., 2016).

The development of online learning can be done by following several development models. Several principles must be considered to create quality, engaging, and practical online learning in achieving learning goals. Online learning must meet three criteria: meaningful, memorable, and motivational (Allen, 2007). For e-learning to be effective and interesting, good preparation is needed. The first step of the preparation is choosing the approach that will be used in developing e-learning. This approach is generally selected by conducting a needs analysis and identifying learning styles, required costs, time, and value-added (Fee, 2009).

Learning activities that can be carried out in online learning are very diverse. A good online learning design makes activities that cannot be done in classroom learning can be done online. Online learning activities include class discussions, journal writing, a shared knowledge base, practical exercises, projects, and receptive activities (Vai and Sosulski, 2015). Activities in online learning, especially in the Moodle learning management system, can also be classified into non-interaction, interactive, and collaboration activities (Rice, 2015). Activities without interaction are carried out with the features of folder/file, labile, link, and web page. Interactive activities include assignments, choices, content pages, feedback, and lessons. Collaborative activities include chat features, forums, glossaries, wikis, and workshops. Moodle is designed to support the social constructivism learning approach. Therefore, one of Moodle's excels in activities is the possibility of collaborative activities between students that can be done well. This view aligns with the functional systemic linguistic approach, which is also strongly influenced by Vygotsky's constructivist theory (Agustien, 2020; Hyland, 2002).

Learning Style

There are very varied views on learning styles. This study will classify learning styles according to Gagne's view, which classifies learning styles into four types and some general characteristics (Gagné et al., 2005). First the visual learning style/verbal learning style. Students at this learning age learn effectively when information is presented visually and in writing. Learners with this style learn effectively with the information presented in textbooks and class notes and prefer to study alone and in a quiet atmosphere. Second, visual/nonverbal learning style. Students with this learning style learn effectively when information is presented visually in pictures or diagrams. Students find learning with visual media materials such as films, videos, animations, maps, and graphics helpful. The online learning environment suits this learning style because it uses graphic information to help him understand and remember concepts and ideas.

Third, tactile/kinesthetic learning style. Students with this style learn best when physically involved in hands-on activities. In addition, students also tend to like to learn with demonstrations, hands-on learning activities, and field activities. Appropriate online learning activities are presentations and discussions both in groups and individually. Fourth, audio/verbal learning style. Students with this learning style can learn well when presented orally, like listening to lessons and participating in group discussions, like listening to the audio, voice narration, and sound effects. The student likes to listen to how it was conveyed and repeat the information aloud to remember it. Online learning activities that suit this learning style are collaboration and group activities.

4. Methods

This study applies a descriptive research method with a qualitative approach. With a qualitative approach, this research will reveal conditions and describe and explore relevant data analysis results obtained from natural situations (Creswell, 2012; Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The research method used is a literature review and a survey conducted from July 28 to August 6, 2021.

The Literature Review was conducted to formulate appropriate text-based learning steps and e-learning platforms for online Indonesian language learning for foreign speakers. The survey was conducted to determine the learning styles of BIPA students.

This research instrument is a questionnaire consisting of forty statement items that students need to respond to. Statements related to learning styles consist of eight statements. Two experts checked the statement items in the questionnaire.

5. Results and Discussions

BIPA Student Learning Style

Learning style is a crucial thing to consider in determining learning design. Learning designs that match student learning styles will help students learn more effectively and be engaging. In the context of classical learning, students' learning styles may be different. What can be done is to prepare several alternative media and learning activities that allow students to have media and activities that suit their learning style.

In online learning, students' learning styles will determine the learning design, the media provided, the activities carried out, and how to evaluate learning. Figure 1 shows the learning styles of BIPA students. The survey results show that the learning styles of BIPA students vary widely. The highest learning style possessed by BIPA students is the tactile/kinesthetic. This learning style shows that students like learning by involving physical activity, presentations, and discussions. The second learning style that students have is the visual learning style/nonverbal learning style. Students with this learning style will learn more effectively through the information presented in pictures and diagrams and through visual media such as films, videos, animations, maps, and graphics. The third learning style is the audio/verbal learning style. Students with this learning style learn more effectively through the information presented orally and by re-listening to material and re-paraphrasing information orally and aloud. The last one is the visual/verbal learning style. Students with this learning style learn effectively when information is presented visually and in written form. Students with visual learning styles/verbal learning styles also prefer to study alone and in quiet conditions. Students with this learning style learn effectively when information is presented visually and in written form. Students with visual learning styles/verbal learning styles also prefer to study alone and in quiet conditions. Students with this learning style learn effectively when information is

presented visually and in written form. Students with visual learning styles/verbal learning styles also prefer to study alone and in quiet conditions.

The survey results showed that all learning styles received high scores, four out of a score range of 1-5 on the questionnaire scale. Therefore, all learning styles must have a balanced portion in the BIPA Level 1 learning design carried out online.

Figure 1: Learning style

E-learning used in BIPA learning

Online learning planning requires an adequate understanding of technology. The essential thing that needs to be done is to choose the right technology to carry out learning. In this study, the e-learning platform used is Moodle (Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment). Moodle was chosen for several reasons: 1) Moodle is a very popular Learning Management System (LMS) used by many educational and training institutions. Moodle has a complete technology ecosystem as an LMS to show various learning activities. 2) Moodle is an LMS designed with a social constructivism approach, which views that learning activities can be carried out well when interacting with the material, making material for other people, and interacting with others (Hyland, 2002; Rice, 2015). The constructivism view is also the basis for a text-based learning approach developed based on the SFL linguistic view and learning theory with Vygotsky's sociocultural approach (Agustien, 2020). Therefore, applying a text-based learning approach is very suitable to be done through Moodle LMS.

The social constructivism approach in Moodle is represented in various types of activities. Activities in Moodle can be classified into three types of activities. 1) Activity without interaction or static. This type of activity allows students to access the material without any interaction, for example, just reading the material. In e-learning, the material can be in the form of web pages, a link to anything on the web, a folder of files, and a label that displays any text or image. 2) Interactive activities that allow students to interact, for example, answering questions, uploading files, or commenting. This type of activity can be in the form of assignment, choice, lesson, or quiz. 3) Social activities that enable collaborative activities. In e-learning, this activity can be facilitated in chat (live online chat), forums, glossaries, Wikis, and workshops (Horton, 2012; Rice, 2015).

Online learning

The view of systemic functional linguistics gave birth to a learning approach called genre-based learning or text-based learning. Text-based learning has several essential principles. Text-based learning emphasizes the importance of context (Accurso & Gebhard, 2020; Beverley Derewianka & Jones, 2010b; Hyland, 2007; Lo & Jeong, 2018; Tuan, 2011), assumes that students learn the language, learn through language, and about language (Beverly Derewianka & Jones, 2016; Emilia, 2016).

Language is seen as a social activity. Language teaching is carried out as explicit teaching (Beverly Derewianka & Jones, 2016; Emilia, 2016; Tuan, 2011). Text-based learning in BIPA learning can be implemented through Moodle LMS and considering the learning styles of BIPA students. The learning design developed by considering aspects of student learning styles, linguistic approaches, and the learning management system used can be described in the following diagram.

Figure 2: learning design

The text-based learning model is described in the form of the teaching-learning cycle (Agustien, 2020; Chaisiri, 2010; Beverly Derewianka & Jones, 2016; Feez & Joyce, 1998). The learning cycle model varies but emphasizes the same thing: the importance of building knowledge about the topic to be studied, the importance of giving model texts that can be used as references by students, the importance of cooperation, and the importance of doing activities individually. (Emilia, 2016). The SFL approach in learning consists of several stages of learning, which include building knowledge of the field, modelling, joint construction, and independent construction (Abbaszadeh, 2013; Agustien, 2020; Chaisiri, 2010; Dirgeyasa, 2016; Emilia, 2016; Kartika-Ningsih & Gunawan, 2019; J. R. Martin, 2009; Nurlaelawati & Novianti, 2017; Pujiyanto et al., 2014).

Each phase in learning is carried out with several activities. In the Knowledge of the Field (BKoF) building stage, the learning activities carried out include students being given text, reading and answering questions about the text, identifying difficult words, learning language skills and understanding grammar, and telling or discussing the content of the text, and develop thinking, critically about the text by responding to the teacher's questions. In the second stage (modelling), several activities are carried out: explaining the text (content, structure, and organization), reading and answering questions about the text, and identifying the structure and linguistic features. In the third stage, the joint construction of learning activities carried out is forming groups, providing written charts as a guide in writing, writing texts in groups, guiding groups, and students consulting with teachers, publishing, and getting input on texts. The last stage, independent construction, is carried out through learning activities: work or create texts independently, students consult with teachers and publish texts made.

No	Learning Stages	Moodle Activities	Media
1	Building Knowledge of the Field (BKoF)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lessons • Content page • SCORM • Glossaries • Quiz 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Write text • Audio • Videos
2	Modelling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content page • Lessons 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Write text • Audio

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SCORM • Glossaries • Quiz 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Videos
3	Joint Construction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lessons • SCORM • Wiki • Forum • Workshop • Live online chat • Assignment (group) • Google docs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Write text • Audio • Videos
4	Independent Construction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop • Assignment • Live chat • Quiz 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Write text • Audio • Videos • Google Docs

Table 1: Learning stages with a text-based approach and activities in Moodle.

The learning steps applying the text-based approach and the e-learning features that can be an option on Moodle are illustrated in figure 3 below. Each stage of online text-based learning is carried out with several choices of e-learning features. The e-learning features are adjusted to the characteristics of the topics, activities, and learning methods used. The options are open-ended and do not have to be used again when the learning topic changes.

Thus, it can be concluded that Moodle provides high flexibility and strongly supports text-based learning implemented through e-learning. Moodle's choice of activities and activity management system aligns with a text-based learning approach. The choice of activities that can be done through e-learning helps in designing interesting and varied learning activities. Thus, students are expected to learn effectively and still be able to maintain their learning motivation.

Figure 3: Learning steps and e-learning features used.

6. Conclusion

A study of the learning styles of BIPA students conducted through a survey concluded that the most dominant learning style of BIPA students was the tactile/kinesthetic learning style (4,4). This shows that BIPA students like and tend to learn more effectively and activities involving physical activity, presentations, and group discussions. Students' following learning style is the Visual/nonverbal learning style (4,3). Students learn more effectively through pictures, diagrams, and visual media such as films, videos, animations, maps, and graphics. The third learning style is the

Audio/verbal learning style (4.14), which shows that BIPA students like learning that is carried out by conveying information orally.

The literature review shows that text-based learning approaches have positively impacted language learning. However, in BIPA learning, its application has not been widely done. The application of text-based learning in online BIPA learning also needs to pay attention to varied learning styles. BIPA learning with varied learning styles, especially tactile/kinesthetic learning styles and learning styles, in accordance with learning with a text-based approach. Text-based learning is also possible online through Moodle's Learning Management System (LMS). Text-based and Moodle-based learning approaches are very suitable because they are developed based on the same paradigm, namely social constructivism. With this view, one of the focuses of learning activities is social, collaborative, and group activities. Moodle can facilitate various online text-based learning activities with various features and technologies.

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